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HENREITTA D. MIRANDA

Faculty

Bulacan State University- Sarmiento

henreitta.miranda@bulsu.edu.ph

“AFTER THE NOISE”

No plans laid,
No trainings paid,
Happy as we carry the bundle of joy,
Sleepless nights await...
Hushing and cradling them in our arms.

House filled with shrieking voice,
Juggling cooking, washing, and tending,
Time has fled...
Gone too fast...

The house is now filled with silence,
No rushing and shouting.
Replaced by chatter of the box
Food on the table, no one dares ask.

Blurry vision, shaking hands,
Trying to sit upright
To check from afar
Waiting for the familiar figure jumping out of the car.